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**SELF-EFFICACY AS PREDICTOR OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN BIOLOGY IN
POST BASIC SCHOOLS OF ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study examines self-efficacy as predictor of students' academic achievement in biology in post basic schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. This study employed a predictive correlation research design. Population of the study consist of 48,760 of all the senior secondary school SS II biology students in Adamawa state with sample of 300 SS II biology students from six selected senior secondary schools. Two instruments were used for data collection namely: Self Efficacy Scale developed by Albert Bandura in (1977) (SES) and a proforma of SS II Biology Terminal Results (BTR). The face and construct validity were determined. Data obtained were subjected to a Cronbach alpha and reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that mastery experience predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State ($r = 0.69$; $t = 11.42$; $p < 0.05$), Vicarious experiences predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State ($r = 0.57$; $t = 8.86$; $p < 0.05$), Verbal persuasion predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State ($r = 0.62$; $t = 10.34$; $p < 0.05$). It was recommended that school administrators should create structured opportunities for students to engage in reflective practices. Biology teachers should encourage to incorporate peer modeling and collaborative learning activities into their teaching.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Mastery Experience, Vicarious Experience, Verbal Persuasion, Biology Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

The growth of science and technology in developing countries like Nigeria has increased the need for citizens to engage in science education. Science education is vital in daily life as it encourages students to explore natural phenomena, equips them with scientific thinking skills, and prepares them to take responsibility for global challenges (Adelaja, 2019). It plays a critical role in building the human capital necessary for the socio-economic, scientific, and technological progress of any nation. Acknowledging its importance, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) incorporated integrated science subjects into the secondary school curriculum and designated biology as a key subject at the senior secondary level. Biology, as a scientific discipline, examines how living organisms function and interact with their environment (Ezenwabachili & Okoli, 2021). Despite its relevance, students' performance in biology has remained consistently low when compared with

number of students enrolment, as highlighted by various researchers (Obialor & Osuafor, 2016; Irede & Okoli, 2019; Onu, Anyaegbunam & Uzoigwe, 2020; Mbaegbu & Osuafor, 2023). Several factors have been identified as contributing to this underachievement. These include ineffective teaching strategies employed by many biology teachers, the abstract and complex nature of certain topics such as cell division, genetics, variation, and evolution, as well as external influences like peer pressure, students' self-perception, motivation, and self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy refers to a students' confidence in their ability to plan and carry out actions needed to accomplish specific tasks in school setting (Gutiérrez-García & Landeros Velázquez, 2018). It is not necessarily about a learners' actual competence, but rather their belief in their capability to perform tasks under particular circumstances. In this study, self-efficacy encompasses: mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional states. According to Maliha and Sarwat (2019), as well as Veerman and Duchatelet (2024), individuals with high self-efficacy tend to set ambitious goals, commit more effort, and persist longer in the face of difficulties. Study by Meng and Zhang (2024) also demonstrated a strong connection between academic self-efficacy, student engagement, and academic success. Observing peers or educators successfully conduct experiments or solve complex biological problems can enhance a student's belief in their own capabilities (Schunk, 2018; Usher & Pajares, 2020; Zimmerman, 2021). Further evidence suggests that when students feel supported and recognized in their school environment, their self-efficacy grows, equipping them to better handle academic challenges (Zhou & Brown, 2019; Demareva, Negash & Sime, 2024). However, findings by Carroll, McCauley, and Grenon (2024) showed that students often feel less confident performing scientific skills than they do answering theoretical questions. Among the sources of self-efficacy, mastery experiences were identified as the most significant in building confidence in scientific competencies.

Studies by Obumse and Nwokedi (2021), and Tengaa (2024) reported a meaningful positive correlation between students' self-efficacy beliefs in science and their performance in mathematics. Conversely, other researchers such as Bwenvu (2023), Pratiwi, Laily, and Sholichah (2021), and Balami (2015) found no significant link between learners' self-efficacy and academic outcomes. Meanwhile, Anierobi, Nwogbo, Ogbe, and Oyeyemi (2022) observed a low but positive relationship between students' academic motivation, self-efficacy, and academic achievement. In light of these mixed findings, the present study seeks to investigate the extent to which self-efficacy can serve as a predictor of students' academic performance in biology at post-basic schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In today's dynamic and competitive global economy, there are concerned on decline of performance in biology in West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner of Biology in 2023. The report identified candidates' weakness under the following subheading: poor spellings of some biological terms, poor application of knowledge, inability to relate and state observable structures of organism and their functions, not giving titles to drawing among others. The consistently low academic performance of students has become a major concern for parents, educators, and policymakers across Nigeria, especially in the North-east states. Among the numerous factors that impact student achievement, self-efficacy has gained recognition as a crucial determinant. Recent studies indicate that learners with stronger self-efficacy tend to adopt more effective learning strategies, show greater persistence when facing academic difficulties, and generally perform better in their studies (Ogunyemi et al., 2021; Okeke & Umeokafor, 2023). However, despite the expanding literature on self-efficacy and academic success, there is still limited understanding of how self-efficacy specifically affects the academic performance of

biology students in post-basic schools within Adamawa State, Nigeria. This study aims to investigate whether self-efficacy may predict academic performance among biology students in post-basic school students of Adamawa State Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to examine self-efficacy as predictor of Students' academic achievement in Biology in post basic schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the Study seeks to examine whether:

1. Mastery experience predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.
2. Vicarious experience predicts Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.
3. Verbal persuasion predicts Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions are raised to guide the Study;

1. What is the level of mastery experiences of Biology Students' academic achievement in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of Vicarious Experiences of Biology Students' academic achievement in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of Verbal persuasion of Biology Students' academic achievement in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and was tested at 0.05 levels of significance to guide the Study.

- HO₁:** Mastery Experience does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.
- HO₂:** Vicarious Experiences does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.
- HO₃:** Verbal persuasion Experiences does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

The theory adopted for this study is the Social Cognitive Learning Theory (SCLT) by Albert Bandura (1977). The theory proposes that that learning and behavior are influenced by a triadic reciprocal interaction between personal behaviors, cognitive process and environmental influence. SCT emphasizes the role of self-efficacy, a person's belief in their capability to perform a specific task or achieve a goal. This belief is influenced by five primary sources of self-efficacy namely; mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social persuasion and physiological and emotional state. Triadic reciprocal causation, sometimes called reciprocal determinism, proposes that behavior is influenced by three interlocking factors: Personal (internal cognitive factors and individual characteristics), Behavioral (actions and reactions), Environmental

(social or physical context). Thus, by identifying variables of self-efficacy, educators can design the strategies that can boost students’ confidence, attitude and cognitive characteristics which may improve their biology performance. This research can therefore examine the self-efficacy variables and the performance of the students; thus, can help enlighten the educational practices in the Nigerian secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a predictive correlational research design. The study was conducted in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study population comprised 48,760 Senior Secondary School (SS II) biology students across the state. A sample of 300 SS II biology students was selected from six senior secondary schools located within three educational zones. The schools were chosen using a purposive sampling technique, after which 50 biology students were randomly selected from each school using simple random sampling, resulting in a total sample size of 300 students. Two main instruments were used for data collection. The first was the “Self-Efficacy Scale (SES)” developed by Albert Bandura (1977), a standardized 15-item questionnaire designed to assess students’ self-efficacy across three key dimensions: mastery experience, vicarious experience, and verbal persuasion. Responses were recorded using five likert scale with the following options: Very True (VT), Mostly True (MT), Moderately True (MT), Slightly True (ST), and Not at All True (NAAT). The second instrument was a “Biology Terminal Results (BTR)” proforma, which captured students’ academic performance in biology across the three school terms. These records were obtained from school examination officers and were officially approved by the school management board. To ensure the validity of the instruments, three experts in Educational Psychology from the Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education at Modibbo Adama University reviewed them for face and construct validity. A pilot test was conducted with 50 SS II biology students from a school outside the main study area to determine the reliability of the SES. The data from this pilot test were analyzed using Cronbach’s alpha, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The instruments were administered by the researcher with the assistance of three trained research assistants. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. To test the hypotheses, linear regression was used at a 0.05 level of significance. A p-value less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypotheses; otherwise, do not reject.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the level of mastery experiences of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation of the level of mastery experiences of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	n=300	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	I am confident in my ability to perform well in biology experiments."		3.50	0.63	MT
2	I feel that I can successfully understand complex biological concepts after studying them.		3.07	0.71	MDT
3	When I encounter difficult topics in biology, I am confident that I can master them		2.86	1.09	MDT
4	I believe that my past successes in biology motivate me to achieve even more in the subject.		3.68	0.76	MT
5	I can effectively apply what I have learned in biology to solve problems or conduct experiments.		3.34	0.50	MDT
	Grand Mean		3.29	0.74	MDT

Key: S.D = Standard deviation; MT = Mostly True; MDT = Moderate True

Table 1 shows that out of 5 mastery experiences of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria demonstrated mostly true in items 1 and 4, while moderate true in items 2, 3, and 5. With a grand mean of 3.29, shows that mastery experiences of Biology Students' have moderate true.

Research Question 2: What is the level of Vicarious Experiences of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of the level of Vicarious Experiences of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	I feel more capable in biology when I see my classmates succeed in their projects.	2.28	0.87	ST
2	Watching others perform well in biology motivates me to improve my own skills.	3.07	0.71	MDT
3	I learn better in biology when I observe my peers discussing challenging topics.	3.86	1.09	MT
4	Seeing my friends' enthusiasm for biology inspires me to engage more in the subject.	3.28	0.76	MDT
5	I believe that observing successful students in biology helps me feel more confident in my abilities.	2.04	0.34	ST
	Grand Mean	2.91	0.75	MDT

Key: S.D = Standard deviation; MT = Mostly True; MDT = Moderate True; ST = Slightly True

Table 2 shows that out of 5 vicarious experiences of Biology students in post basic schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria demonstrated mostly true in item 8, slightly true in items 6 and 10 while moderate true in items 7 and 9. With a grand mean of 2.91, indicated that vicarious experiences of Biology Students' have moderate true.

Research Question 3: What is the level of verbal persuasion of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria?

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation of the level of Verbal Persuasion of Biology Students in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

S/No	Items n = 300	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	When my teachers encourage me, I feel more confident in my ability to succeed in biology.	2.28	0.87	ST
2	Positive feedback from my classmates boosts my belief in my biology skills.	1.07	0.31	ST
3	I feel motivated to study biology when my friends express their confidence in my abilities.	2.86	1.09	MDT
4	Hearing my teachers say that I can do well in biology makes me believe I can.	3.68	0.76	MT
5	Encouragement from my family regarding my biology studies helps me feel more capable.	2.07	0.43	ST
	Mean	2.39	0.69	ST

Key: S.D = Standard deviation; MT = Mostly True; MDT = Moderate True; ST = Slightly True

Table 3 shows that out of 5 verbal experiences of Biology students in post basic schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria demonstrated mostly true in item 14, slightly true in items 11, 12 and 15 while moderate true in item 13. With a grand mean of 2.39, indicated that verbal experiences of Biology Students' have slightly true.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses were tested using linear and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: Mastery Experience does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Table 4a: Linear Regression Analysis of Mastery Experience on Students' Academic Achievement.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	55.83	1	55.83	62.153	0.00*
Residual	60.18	67	0.89		
Total	116.01	68			

Table 4b: Regression Model Summary of Relative contribution of Mastery Experience on students' academic achievement.

Variables	B	SE	Beta	r	R ²	Adj R	T
Constant	7.54	0.66					11.40
Mastery Experience	-1.59	0.20	-0.69	0.69	0.48	0.47	-7.88

Table 4a-b showed that there is a significant difference between the various R values, F = 62.153 (df 1), p < 0.05. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore the null hypothesis of no significance is rejected. This means that mastery experience predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State. The result also showed that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between mastery experience on students' academic achievement (r = 0.69; t = 11.42; p < 0.05)

H₀₂: Vicarious Experiences does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Table 5a: Linear Regression Analysis of Vicarious Experiences on Students' Academic Achievement.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	38.53	1	38.53	33.32	0.00*
Residual	77.48	67	1.15		
Total	116.01	68			

Table 5b: Regression Model Summary of Relative contribution of Vicarious Experiences on Students' Academic Achievement.

Variables	B	SE	Beta	r	R ²	Adj R	T
Constant	6.70	0.75					8.86
Vicarious Experiences	-0.14	0.25	-0.57	0.57	0.33	0.32	-5.77

Table 5a-b showed that there is a significant difference between the various R values, F = 33.32 (df 1), p < 0.05. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore the null hypothesis of no significance is rejected. This means that vicarious experiences predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools

of Adamawa State. The result showed that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between vicarious experiences on students' academic achievement ($r = 0.57$; $t = 8.86$; $p < 0.05$).

H₀₃: Verbal persuasion Experiences does not significantly predict Students' academic achievement in Biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Table 6a: Linear Regression Analysis of Verbal Persuasion on Students' Academic Achievement.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	44.97	1	44.97	42.41	0.00*
Residual	71.03	67	1.06		
Total	116.01	68			

Table 6b: Regression Model Summary of Relative contribution of Verbal Persuasion on Students' Academic Achievement.

Variables	B	SE	Beta	r	R ²	Adj R	T
Constant	6.27	0.60					10.34
Verbal Persuasion	-1.30	0.20	-0.62	0.62	0.38	0.37	-6.51

Table 6a-b showed that there is a significant difference between the various R values, $F = 42.41$ ($df 1$), $p < 0.05$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore the null hypothesis of no significance is rejected. This indicated that verbal persuasion predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State. The result showed that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between verbal persuasion on students' academic achievement ($r = 0.62$; $t = 10.34$; $p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

This study found that mastery experience predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State. These findings align with Veerman and Duchatelet (2024) and Kassaw, Demareva, Negash, and Sime (2024) who found that mastery experiences and social persuasion were effectively enhanced through simulation-based learning environments that foster informal interactions. Likewise, Meng and Zhang (2024) reported a strong and positive relationship between academic self-efficacy, student engagement, and academic performance, further supporting the central role of self-efficacy in academic success. Similarly, Capa, Aydin, Uzuntiryaki, Kondakci, and Ceylandag (2018) established that mastery experience had a direct effect on students' self-efficacy in chemistry. They also found a mediating effect, where mastery experiences accounted for 50% of the variance in self-efficacy related to cognitive skills in chemistry, through both direct and indirect influences. In the same vein, Achufusi and Utaka (2021) observed a modest positive relationship between mastery experience and student motivation, concluding that improved self-efficacy derived from mastery experiences contributed to better performance in physics. In another study, Carroll, McCauley, and Grenon (2024) noted that students generally exhibited lower self-efficacy in performing scientific skills than in answering theoretical questions. Nevertheless, mastery experience emerged as the most significant factor influencing self-efficacy in science-related tasks, reinforcing the findings across various educational disciplines. However, while Veerman and Duchatelet (2024) acknowledged the importance of self-efficacy, they also pointed out that its effect is incomplete without considering other contributing factors like vicarious experiences, emotional states and broader contextual influences.

The findings found that vicarious experiences predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic

Schools of Adamawa State ($r = 0.57$; $t = 8.86$; $p < 0.05$), with a grand mean of 2.91. This finding agreed with Veerman and Duchatelet (2024) who reported that vicarious experiences have a significant and positive relationship with academic achievement, indicating that observing others can effectively influence student performance. Similarly, Meng and Zhang (2024) found a strong association between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement. In a related study, Tom et al. (2020) revealed a statistically significant positive correlation. This suggests that vicarious learning not only influences academic outcomes but also behavioral development. These insights imply that biology teachers should create learning environments that enhance vicarious experiences, such as peer modeling, collaborative experiments, and demonstration-based instruction, to improve student engagement and achievement. On the contrary, Capa et al. (2018) found no mediating effect of vicarious experience on students' academic performance. This suggests that while vicarious experience may be influential in some contexts, its effectiveness could depend on other interacting variables or specific educational settings.

The study revealed that verbal persuasion predicts academic achievement of students in biology in Post Basic Schools of Adamawa State ($r = 0.62$; $t = 10.34$; $p < 0.05$), with a grand mean of 2.39. This finding is consistent with the study by Ucar and Sungur (2017) indicated that verbal persuasion significantly predicts students' academic achievement in science subjects. Their results suggest that students with strong self-efficacy particularly in the form of verbal encouragement tend to be more behaviorally, emotionally and cognitively engaged in science learning, leading to improved academic performance. In a similar vein, Hwang, Choi, Lee, Culver, and Hutchison (2016) revealed that verbal self-efficacy positively predicted students' academic achievement during the first semester of 9th grade. Additionally, Bin-Hassan, Bin-Hossain, and Islam (2014) reported a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement, identifying key contributing variables such as mastery experiences, vicarious learning, verbal persuasion, and physiological arousal as foundational to the development of self-efficacy beliefs among students. Moreover, Meng and Zhang (2024) also confirmed a strong and favorable correlation among academic self-efficacy, student engagement, and academic performance, reinforcing the broader importance of self-efficacy across learning domains among students. Conversely, Achufusi and Utaka (2021) found that self-efficacy did not significantly impact students' academic achievement in physics, suggesting that the influence of self-efficacy may vary depending on subject area or instructional context.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, and verbal persuasion had a moderate influence on biology students' academic achievement. Additionally, the results revealed that self-efficacy serves as a positive predictor of students' academic achievement in biology in post-basic schools in Adamawa State. When students possess well-developed self-efficacy, it enhances their ability to grasp biological concepts effectively, ultimately leading to improved academic achievement in biology.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. School administrators should create structured opportunities for students to engage in reflective practices. Encouraging learners to revisit their past academic successes, analyze the strategies that contributed to those achievements, and apply similar approaches in future tasks.
2. Biology teachers should encourage to incorporate peer modeling and collaborative learning activities into their teaching. Allowing students to observe their peers successfully and sharing success stories especially from individuals with similar

backgrounds can boost students' self-efficacy.

3. School management should organize professional development workshops for biology teachers focused on the effective use of constructive feedback.

REFERENCES

- Achufusi, N. N., & Utaka, J. N. (2021). Self-efficacy and motivation as correlates of secondary school students' academic achievement in physics. *Unizik Journal of STM Education*, 4(1), 19-28.
- Adamawa State Post Primary School Management Board (2023).
- Adelaja, S. (2019). Nigeria: How to develop a nation through science and technology. Retrieved from <https://allafrica.com/stories/201601110147.html> on 9/9/2023
- Akram, B., & Ghazanfar, L. (2014). Self efficacy and academic performance of the students of Gujrat University, Pakistan. *Academic Research International*, 5(1), 283.
- Anierobi, E. I., Nwogbo, V. N., Ogbe, I. J., & Oyeyemi, A. A. (2022). Academic motivation and self-efficacy as determinants of academic performance of secondary school students in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Advances in Research*, 765-774.
- Balami, Y. G. (2015). Relationship between self-efficacy belief and academic achievement of distance learner in National Teachers Institute (NTI) Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(2), 80-84.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191-215.
- Bin-Hassan, M. Z., Bin-Hossain, M. T., & Islam, M. A., (2014). Factors Affecting Self-Efficacy Towards Academic Performance: A Study on Polytechnic Students in Malaysia. *Adv. Environ. Biol.*, 8(9), 695-705.
- Bwenvu, G. (2023). Students' Self-efficacy and Academic Performance Makerere University. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 12(1), 101-117.
- Capa, A., Aydin, Y., Uzuntiryaki, Kondakci, E., & Ceylandag, R. (2018). The relationship between vicarious experience, social persuasion, physiological state, and chemistry self-efficacy: The role of mastery experience as a mediator. *Psychology in the Schools*, 55(10), 1224-1238.
- Carroll, S., McCauley, V., & Grenon, M. (2024). Science self-efficacy beliefs of upper primary students in Ireland. *International Journal of Science Education*, 46(6), 503-523.
- Ezenwabachili, C.G. & Okoli, J.N. (2021). Effect of flip classroom and think-pair-share instructional strategies on students' retention in Biology in Enugu education zone. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 7(3), 70-79.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National policy on education. NERDC Press.
- Gutiérrez-García, A. G. & Landeros-Velázquez M. G. (2018). Academic self-efficacy and anxiety, as a critical incident in female and male University students. *Revista Costarricense de Psicología*, 37(1), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.22544/rcps.v37i01.01> On 16 August, 2020.
- Hwang, M. H., Choi, H. C., Lee, A., Culver, J. D., & Hutchison, B. (2016). The relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement: A 5-year panel analysis. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 25, 89-98.
- Irede, E.A. & Okoli, J. N. (2019). Teachers' use of science writing heuristics in Biology instruction and its effect on students' acquisition of science process skills. *IOSR Journal of Research and Method in education (IOSR-JRME)*, 9(6), 17-26.
- Kassaw, C., Demareva, V., Negash, M., & Sime, Y. (2024). Psychosocial determinants of academic achievement in Ethiopian higher education students, 2024. Systematic review and Meta-analysis. *Heliyon*.

- Maliha, N. & Sarwat, I. (2019). Academic self-efficacy as a predictor of academic achievement of students in pre-service teacher training programs. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 41(1), 33-42.
- Mbaegbu, S.C. & Osuafor, M.A. (2023). Effect of ethnobiology instructional approach on academic achievement of secondary school students in biology in Onitsha education zone. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, 10(3), 1-6.
- Meng, Q., & Zhang, Q. (2023). The influence of academic self-efficacy on university students' academic performance: The mediating effect of academic engagement. *Sustainability*, 15(7), 576.
- Obialor, C. O. & Osuafor, O. (2016). Effect of project work on students achievement in secondary school biology. Unplished M.SC. (Ed), Thesis), Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Obumse, N. A. P., & Nwokedi, O. J. (2021). Self-efficacy as correlates of academic achievement of secondary school students in Anambra State. *COOU Journal of Educational Research.*, 6(1), 188 – 198.
- Ogunyemi, O., Adesina, A., & Adebayo, A. (2021). The role of self-efficacy in academic performance among biology students in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(2), 345-359. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000456>
- Okeke, P. I., & Umeokafor, N. (2023). Self-efficacy and its impact on academic achievement in post-basic education: A case study of biology students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science Education*, 45(3), 455-472. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2022.2041234>
- Onu, W., Anyaegbunam, N. & Uzoigwe, A. (2020) Improving Biology students' interest and achievement through collaborative instructional strategy. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 33(2), 9-20.
- Pratiwi L. E., Laily N., & Sholichah I. F., (2021). The relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement. *Journal Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik Engineering Social Science and Health International Conference*, 1(2), 851-85.
- Schunk, D. H. (2018). *Learning theories: An educational perspective* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Tengaa, P. E. (2024). Students' self-efficacy in mathematics academic achievement: Do teachers' personality traits matter?. *Edukasiana: Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan*, 3(1), 128-142.
- Tom, K. O. Onyango, Peter Jo Aloka, Pamela A. Raburu, (2020). Vicarious Experience and Delinquent Behaviour Modification: Evidence Among Students in Secondary Schools in Kenya, *International Journal of Brain and Cognitive Sciences*, 9(1), 9-15.
- Ucar, F. M. & Sungur, S. (2017). The role of perceived classroom goal structures, self-efficacy, and engagement in student science achievement. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 35(2), 149-168.
- Usher, E. L., & Pajares, F. (2020). Sources of self-efficacy in school: Critical review of the literature and future directions. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(1), 1-28.
- Veerman, A., & Duchatelet, D. (2024). Fostering social persuasion as a source of self-efficacy in negotiating through simulation design. *European Political Science* 23, 156–178.
- West African Examination Council (2023) *Chief Examiners Report, Lagos; WAEC*.
- Zhou, M., & Brown, D. (2019). Educational learning theories: 2nd Edition. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(4), 1-20.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2021). The role of self-efficacy in self-regulated learning. In D. H. Schunk & J. A. Greene (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (pp. 19-32). Routledge.